

Voltage and concentration gradient across membraneless interface generated next to hydrogels: relation to glycocalyx

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Next to many hydrophilic surfaces, including those of biological cells and tissues, a layer of water that effectively excludes solutes and particles can be generated. This interfacial water is the subject of research aiming for practical applications such as removal of salts, pathogens or manipulation of biomolecules. Yet, the exact mechanism of its creation is still elusive, because its persistence and extension contradict hydrogen-bond dynamics and electric double layer predictions. The experimentally recorded negative voltage of this interfacial water remains to be properly explained. Even less is known about the nature of such water layers in biological systems. We present experimental evidence for ion and particle exclusion as a result of separation of ionic charges with distinct diffusion rates across a liquid junction at the gel/water interface and the subsequent repulsion of ions of a given sign by a like-charged gel surface. Gels represent features of biological interfaces (in terms of functional groups and porosity) and are subject to biologically relevant chemical triggers. Our results show that gels with $-\text{OSO}_3^-$ and $-\text{COO}^-$ groups can effectively generate ion- and particle-depleted regions of water reaching over 100 μm and having negative voltage up to -30 mV. Exclusion distance and electric potential depend on the liquid junction potential at the gel/water interface and on the concentration gradient at the depleted region/bulk interface, respectively. The voltage and extension of these ion- and particle-depleted water layers can be effectively modified by CO_2 (respiratory gas) or KH_2PO_4 (cell metabolite). Possible implications pertain to biological unstirred water layers and a cell's bioenergetics.

Introduction

It has been recognized that many hydrophilic surfaces of biological or synthetic origin can generate an extensive layer of water that effectively excludes solutes and particles.¹⁻¹³ This interfacial water layer can extend up to hundreds of micrometers from the surface and has been exploited for designing desalination devices,¹⁴ pre-concentration of biomolecules^{15,16} or generation of pathogen-resistant surfaces.¹⁷ One of the first observations of long-range depletion zones existing next to biological cells was made by Derjaguin in 1984.² Apart from many possible practical applications and biological implications, the mechanism of formation of these depletion zones (largely devoid of ions and particles) is not yet fully understood.¹⁸⁻²² There are two main lines of thought: (i) the one advocating for the depletion zone being an intrinsic property of the surface and its interaction solely with water⁴ and (ii) those that refer to it as an electrokinetic phenomenon next to ion-selective surfaces and recognize the need for a driving force e.g. in the form of applied voltage, gravity or capillary force.^{1,7,14,16} The first approach (i) describes interfacial water as having a different structure and, in essence, a distinct chemical composition than bulk water due to release of protons and acquisition of net negative charge.^{4,23,24} Experimentally recorded negative voltage of the depletion zone served to support this hypothesis.^{4,25} Although some degree of autodissociation of water is taking place, especially next to charged interfaces,²⁶ the possibility of existence of such extensive negatively charged water regions raises serious concerns.^{20,22,27} To account for apparent electric negativity and stability of the depletion zones (in spite of fast dynamics of the hydrogen bonding network), the quantum electrodynamics

theory provided explanation based on coherent domains of water.²⁸ The electrokinetic approach (ii), on the other hand, deals well with predicting behaviour and modelling the phenomena, yet it does not address the question of negative voltage within the depletion zone.²⁹ One attempt in this regard was made by Schurr, who suggested that an electric potential difference between the zone and bulk solution may result from concentration gradient of electroneutral ionic solutes.³⁰ Nevertheless, the electric potential gradient maintained between different parts of the same solution, without any physical barrier separating them, remains an open and intriguing issue. Due to this feature, the theory of a depletion (or exclusion) zone representing a different physical state of water, essentially immiscible with the bulk and possessing intrinsic net negative charge is still considered, despite its many surrounding controversies.^{4, 20, 22-25, 27, 28} In this work, we aim to (i) further clarify the mechanism behind the depletion zone formation from an electrokinetic perspective, with special focus on the origin of negative voltage (as we show explainable within this framework) and to (ii) explore the possibility to control a depletion zone's main characteristics – exclusion distance and voltage. Very importantly, we aim to translate this knowledge into the biology field as there is a lack of recognition of the possible role played by the physico-chemical phenomena, proper for particular states of matter (here gels), in living organisms.

Our previous works have already addressed the nature of the depletion zone phenomenon and indicated its possible biological implications at a cellular level.^{11,12} Further to this end, there are several manifestations of depletion zones being present in biological systems. One of those is an endothelial surface layer (ESL) existing next to a blood vessels' lining and effectively excluding blood cells and plasma solutes to a distance of micrometers. ESL is composed in 99,9993 % of water and it remains enigmatic how this layer made mostly of water may prevent cells from approaching the vessel's wall.³¹ Yet ESL is only generated next to gelatinous glycocalyx coating, rich in negatively charged sulfate groups and possessing all

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characteristics of a selectively permeable (permselective) surface (suggested to be prerequisite for depletion zone formation).³² The Glycocalyx envelops also red blood cells (RBC), which repel each other to a distance significantly greater than that predicted by electrostatic interactions due to a negative charge of the RBC surface. In fact, a recent study has shown that in order to account for this repulsion distance, extracellular voltage existing next to (and not across) the cell membrane of a RBC has to be taken into account.³³ In this study we use depletion zone inducing surfaces represented by hydrogels, based on alginate and agarose with fucoidan as an additive, because of their mesh-like porous structure and specific functional groups (-OSO₃⁻ and -COO⁻) content, both features characteristic also for glycocalyx and the extracellular matrix. Fucoidan, in particular is a highly sulfated natural polysaccharide and as such was suggested to act as an analogue of heparan or chondroitin sulfate (abundant in glycocalyx).^{34, 35} We expose those gel-based surfaces to biologically relevant stimuli (CO₂, KH₂PO₄) in order to shed new light on specific biological phenomena that might be manifestations of naturally occurring depletion zones.

Experimental

Hydrogels' preparation

Hydrogels with varying concentration of either -OSO₃⁻ or -COO⁻ functional groups were synthesized in order to examine the effect of chemical identity and density of the charges on the generation of the depletion zones.

Agarose gels. Agarose gels (AG) with a varying ratio of high electroendosmosis, (HE) (-OSO₃⁻ ≤ 0.2 %) to low electroendosmosis, (LE) (-OSO₃⁻ ≤ 0.1 %) agarose were prepared by dissolving agarose powders HE and LE (PRONA, Agarosa Basica HE, and Agarosa Basica LE, respectively) in hot deionized (DI) water under constant stirring. Gel density was kept constant at 1.5 % (defined by the dry weight of the polymer(s) dissolved in given volume of DI water) and specific preparations with a decreasing content of charged functional groups consisted of: (1) pure HE; (2) HE/LE = 2, (3) HE/LE = 1; (4) HE/LE = ½ and (5) pure LE. After dissolution, agarose sols were poured into cylindrical molds, left to complete gelation at room temperature and afterwards cut into discs of approximate thickness of 1-2 mm. Gel discs were dialyzed against DI water for 72 h and stored in DI water in enclosed containers at 4°C for 7 days before use. Different storing times were also tested to verify the effect of gel ageing on the depletion zone formation.

Calcium alginate gels. Calcium alginate gels (ALG) of varying densities (thus of a different carboxylate groups content) were prepared by dissolving sodium alginate (Alginic acid sodium salt, Sigma Aldrich, CAS: 9005-38-3) in DI water to obtain solutions of: (1) 0.5 %; (2) 1.0 %; (3) 1.5 %; (4) 2.0 % and (5) 2.5 % concentration and their subsequent crosslinking by calcium ion. For the latter purpose, the solutions were poured into 2 ml Eppendorf tubes with holes evenly distributed around the tube and dipped in 0.2 M CaCl₂ for 48 h in order to achieve complete gelation. Multiple holes in the mould enabled faster diffusion of crosslinking Ca²⁺ ions across several diffusion fronts throughout

the alginate solution. However, different designs of the mould can also assure successful gelation. Subsequently, gels were cut into discs (1-2 mm thickness), dialyzed (72 h) and stored in DI water at 4°C for 7 days before being used in the same manner as AG gels.

Agarose-fucoidan gels. Agarose-fucoidan blends (FU) were prepared to obtain gels with constant gel density and a varying amount of -OSO₃⁻ residues. Agarose-fucoidan blends were prepared by adding varying amount of fucoidan (Fucoidan, MW: 242.24g/mol, Purity 95%, Angene, China) to 1.5 % agarose HE solution at temperature window of (75 – 80)°C. The solution was stirred for about 2-4 min. until complete dissolution of fucoidan (visually identified by homogeneous beige color without any particles or clumping). Specific preparations consisted of 1.5 % HE agarose gel containing (1) 0.5 %; (2) 1.0 %; (3) 1.5 %; (4) 2.0 % or (5) 2.5 % (mass/volume) of fucoidan, respectively. Molding, dialysis and storage procedures were the same as described for AG and ALG gels.

Characterization of the gels

Swelling. Swelling is defined by gel's water absorbing ability and depends on the osmotic pressure generated by charged residues within the gel (driving water influx) and is restricted by stiffness of polymer network.³⁶ For the purpose of our study we determined swelling of prepared hydrogels by dipping 1 g of hydrated (freshly prepared) gels in DI water at 25°C and measuring the weight increment at time intervals until reaching equilibrium (maximum water absorption - maximum constant weight). The swelling degree (*Q*) was then calculated in relation to weight of the respective gel sample obtained after shrinking (constant weight of shrunk gel exposed to ambient air at 25°C) as $Q = (W_o - W_d)/W_d$, where *W_o* is the weight of swollen gel at given time interval and *W_d* is weight of shrunk (dry) gel. 5 gel specimens of a given composition were used to calculate the average swelling degree of a particular gel type.

Stiffness. Gel stiffness in our study is expressed in bending angle (θ). The latter is determined by force of gravity causing a gel's deformation under its own weight. Therefore, particularly for agarose gels of constant density (meaning the same weight of dry polymer used for gelation in a given volume of water), bending reflects the ability of gels to hold water depending on the concentration of functional groups. Bending angle was measured by placing a gel sample shaped into rectangular rod on a horizontal plane and leaving a known volume of a gel (0.5 mm x 12 mm x 20 mm) after a fixing point to bend upon gravity. Bending angle (θ) is expressed here as the deflection angle of a gel specimen from a horizontal plane (ESI, Fig. S1). 5 gel specimens of a given composition were used to calculate the average stiffness of a particular gel type.

Conductivity. Conductivity was measured in order to address the ability of hydrogels to support ion transport, a property directly dependent on the concentration of charged (dissociated) functional groups. A measuring microprobe of a conductivity meter (InLab 751 – 4 mm, METTLER TOLEDO, SevenCompact™ Duo S213) was inserted into a gel sample (10 mm x 30 mm x 15 mm) and its conductivity was recorded. 5 gel

specimens of a given composition were used to obtain the average conductivity of a particular gel.

Depletion zone characterization

Particle exclusion. Particle exclusion was used to visualize the depletion zone at the gel/water interface and to measure its extension. Micro-particle suspension was prepared by diluting 1 drop of non-functionalized polystyrene micro-particles (1.0 μm ; analytical standard; 89904; Sigma Aldrich) in 15 ml of DI water. It has to be noted that even in case of non-functionalized hydrophobic particles, they are expected to possess/acquire surface charge in aqueous solution, either from stabilizing agents used in the manufacturing process or due to ions of low charge density that have a tendency to partition to their surfaces.³⁷ Therefore, the microspheres used in our experiments should not be considered *de facto* uncharged. Non-functionalized polystyrene particles usually exhibit negative zeta potentials in an aqueous solution.³⁸

Individual gel disks were immobilized on 35 mm glass-bottom Petri dishes (Ibidi GmbH Germany) and immersed in 4 ml of the microparticle suspension. Alternatively, the suspension was slowly added to a Petri dish containing a gel specimen already immersed in DI water. The latter approach had to be preferably used in case of gels without added fucoidan. Such gels were able to prevent particles from approaching their surfaces, but they were not always able to expel particles from their vicinity. The width of the depletion zone – a region of interfacial solution devoid of microspheres – was measured after the exclusion distance reached stable size (over the course of a few minutes). Zone width was defined as the extension of this particle-free region (averaged over multiple locations – a minimum of 10) measured from the gel surface to particle-rich bulk solution. At least 5 gel specimens of a particular composition were used to measure particle exclusion distance under any given set of conditions.

Voltage. Voltage of the depletion zone and the gel specimen was measured with the use of an electrometer (FD223a, World Precision Instruments (WPI), LLC, USA). Glass microelectrodes were prepared from filamented borosilicate microcapillaries (1.2 mm OD, WPI) pulled by a microelectrode puller (PUL-1000, WPI) under programmed parameters (loops of: heat index 400; force 250 g; distance 0.6 mm; delay 100(1s)) and filled with 3 M KCl. For measurement, individual gel discs were immobilized on 35 mm glass-bottom Petri dishes and immersed in 4 ml of DI water. A reference electrode was then placed in the bulk, distant to the gel surface (and arbitrarily set to 0 V), while the measuring electrode was moved with the use of micromanipulators (Luigs&Neumann, GmbH, Germany) from the bulk toward the gel/water interface and then was entering the gel's body. Electric potential difference (voltage) of the depletion zone and gel's interior with respect to bulk solution was recorded with the use of LabScribe4 software (by iWorx). The distance from the gel surface at which a voltage drop could be first registered (on electrode approaching from the bulk) was then compared to the depletion zone width as determined by particle exclusion.

Additional experiments have been performed with the reference electrode placed in an external bath connected via a salt bridge (agar-KCl) with the experimental bath.

A minimum of 5 repetitions of voltage measurement were performed for every gel sample and a minimum of 5 gel specimens of a particular composition were tested to obtain the average voltage value (of the zone and of the gel) for a given gel type at any given experimental conditions.

Depletion zone modification

In order to address the ability to control depletion zone parameters based on the adopted mechanism of its generation, the effects of solution chemistry and physical properties of a gel were systematically investigated.

Gel's drying. Due to consistent differences in the depletion zone width depending on the gels' storage time (data not shown), gels were subjected to gentle drying in order to mimic the process of ageing.^{39,40} For that purpose, gel discs were dried for 30 min. at 30 °C in an incubator (FRIOCELL, BMT Medical Technology s.r.o, Czech Republic) and then assessed for their ability to induce depletion zone formation following the experimental protocol described in previous sections.

Effect of CO₂. In order to generate ion concentration gradient across the gel/water interface, gels were exposed to either internal or external influx of CO₂. Internal influx was achieved by exposing gel discs immersed in DI water to 3.5 % of CO₂ gas at 25 °C in a controlled atmosphere provided by an incubator. The CO₂ – exposed discs were then placed in fresh DI water and immediately verified for their ability to generate a depletion zone as described in previous sections. Control experiments were performed after subjecting a gel specimen to the same preconditioning (incubator, 25 °C), but without CO₂ exposure. External CO₂ influx was provided by exposing DI water to 3.5 % of CO₂ gas at 25 °C and then immersing gel discs (stored in DI water without gas exposure) in this CO₂-saturated water. Subsequent measurements of depletion zone width and voltage were performed following described protocol. Both internal and external CO₂ exposure time was set to 40 min. It was verified by pH measurements (InLab Ultra-Micro-ISM, METTLER TOLEDO, SevenCompact™ Duo S213) that under our experimental conditions water is saturated with CO₂ after this time period and reaches stable pH = 4.1.

Effect of pH. To account for the chemical identity of the ionic species supporting depletion zone formation, solution pH was adjusted with HCl and the effects were verified against pH change induced by dissolving CO₂. Discrete pH values adjusted by HCl were changing in 0.2 increments from pH = 5.9 (pH of deionized water) to pH = 3.7. Gel discs were immersed in pH-adjusted DI water and assessed for their ability to generate a depletion zone.

Effect of KH₂PO₄. In order to address the influence of solution ionic strength and further confirm the effect of chemical identity of ionic species, gels were immersed in solutions of varying concentration of KH₂PO₄. Specific concentrations of KH₂PO₄ equaled 0.01 M, 0.05 M, 0.10 M and 0.15 M. Solutions become more acidic on increasing concentration, therefore, to account for the effect of protons, corresponding experiments

Fig. 1 Schematic representation of the depletion zone configuration and principles of its formation: Ion concentration gradient at the solution/gel interface drives diffusion of ions across selectively permeable (here negatively charged) gel surface. Due to different diffusion rates (D_+ and D_-) of cations and anions, former penetrate the gel, while following them counterions are repelled from the surface of the same charge to a distance defining depletion zone width. This creates effective separation of charges (depicted in green) across the zone. Cations, attracted by opposing forces created by negatively charged gel surface and by unbalanced anions from solution (in green), concentrate at the solution/zone boundary (shaded region – (a)) and constitute positive terminal of a capacitor which negative terminal is created by gel's surface (shaded area – (b)). Please note, that measured voltage gradient (negative within the zone with respect to bulk) follows expected concentration gradient (red dotted line), although some unbalanced negative charges (in green) are present in the bulk.

were made also for pH-adjusted solutions with pH fixed at 4.1 value. Depletion zone parameters were measured for gels exposed to KH_2PO_4 solutions following described procedures. A minimum of 5 repetitions were performed for voltage and/or particle exclusion measurements at any given experimental conditions (with respect to modified solution chemistry and/or gel structure).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The model of depletion zone generation, as adopted by us and some research groups,^{12,14,16} assumes that the zone can be created as a result of selective permeability of the surface toward ions of a given sign and ensuing separation of charges (cations and anions) across the interface (Fig. 1). In case of a negatively charged gel network (such as the one applied in this work), cations can penetrate through the pores of the gel, while their counterions are left in the solution and are repelled to some distance (defining depletion zone width) by the negatively charged gel's body. At a consequent long-lived transient state, manifested as a depletion zone, no more cations can diffuse through the zone and into the gel as they are immediately attracted back to the solution by their anionic unbalanced counterparts. Those cations, subject to opposing forces, can concentrate at the bulk/depletion zone boundary. Also, the anions are restricted from both: entering the zone and diffusing

indefinitely away to the bulk, due to repulsion caused by the surface and attraction by pre-concentrated cations, respectively. The same principle of exclusion applies to any charged bodies (e. g. colloidal particles) introduced to the system where stable (over an arbitrarily long period of time – in experiments extending to hours) ion depletion zone has been established. The distance to which ions are repelled from the interface depends on: the amount of separated charges and charge density of the interface (non-balanced negative ions in solution and negativity of the gel in this particular case). The latter is defined by the intrinsic properties of a gel, while the former depends on ion concentration (availability) and a force driving ion movement toward the interface, e.g. concentration or electric potential gradient (chemical and electric force, respectively) or fluid advection (e.g. induced by capillary forces).

There are particular predictions that can be made based on the presented model (Fig. 1) and, if confirmed, will allow control over the depletion zone formation. According to the proposed mechanism: (i) the size of the depletion zone depends on the charge of the interface and its porosity (ion-selective permeability); (ii) ionic charges become separated across the depletion zone; (iii) a driving force (non-equilibrium conditions) is necessary for depletion zone formation. In the following sections, we present results of our experiments designed to verify the above statements and enable defined modification of the depletion zone. Furthermore, we aim to explore the origin of the zone's negative voltage that is not explicitly covered by the discussed model (as schematically represented on Fig. 1).

Effect of surface charge and porosity (permselectivity) and nature of the permeating ionic charges

For any given gel type – Ca-alginate (ALG), agarose (AG) and agarose-fucoidan (FU) blends and any experimental conditions, there is a linear correlation between voltage of the gel measured in respect to the bulk solution (further referred to as the gel's internal negativity) and width of the depletion zone formed at the gel's interface (Fig. 2). The gel's negativity depends on the concentration of negatively charged functional groups, therefore, it increases along with the density of alginate gel, and the percentage of high electroendosmosis agarose or fucoidan content, respectively (on moving from bottom left to top right on the graph). FU gels generate the largest depletion zones with the width of $(107.4 \pm 1.4) \mu\text{m}$ – $(120.8 \pm 1.4) \mu\text{m}$ due to the presence of highest amount of free negatively charged functional groups (Fig. 2 and 3). AG gels (with low intrinsic concentration of sulfate groups) give rise to depletion zones widths of $(60.7 \pm 2.4) \mu\text{m}$ to $(82.6 \pm 2.0) \mu\text{m}$. Carboxylate groups are present in high concentrations in alginate, yet they are complexed with Ca^{2+} to form gel structure and the ALG gel induces depletion zones ranging from $(58.9 \pm 2.3) \mu\text{m}$ to $(81.5 \pm 2.8) \mu\text{m}$. The gel's negativity impacts depletion zone formation by providing electrostatic force attracting cations and repelling anions (and acting as a charge-selective gate) as well as by inducing fluid advection (driving directional ion movement) due to the osmotic pressure.³⁶ The latter property is expressed also in the gel's swelling and bending (the latter reflecting mass

Fig. 2 Dependence of the depletion zone width on internal voltage of Ca-alginate (ALG – blue traces); agarose (AG – orange traces) and agarose-fucoidan (FU – green traces) gels. Unshaded, right hand side of the graph: solid lines, filled symbols – gels in DI water; dashed lines, open symbols – dried (aged) gels in DI water. Shaded, left hand side – gels exposed to CO₂: by external (ext.) supply – filled symbols; or by internal (int.) CO₂ supply – open symbols. Horizontal (constant zone's width) line across points pertaining to a gel of given composition under internal or external CO₂ exposure highlights voltage change at constant zone's width depending on direction of CO₂ gradient. Points along individual trend lines correspond to different preparations of a given gel type with concentration of functional groups increasing on moving from bottom left to upper right (e.g. for ALG: 1 → 0.5 %; 2 → 1 %; 3 → 1.5 %; 4 → 2 %; 5 → 2.5 %). Arrows on FU show direction of changes (common to all gels) for a given gel's composition on drying (increase in gel's negativity and in corresponding zone width).

increase at constant volume) that increase with higher concentration of functional groups (ESI, Fig. S1 and S2). Given all the forces and components required for depletion zone formation are present in the system, the factor effectively defining zone width can be reduced to electrostatic repulsion between the surface and ions having the same charge as the latter. This is reflected in zone width showing linear relationship with the gel's charge (expressed in the gel's voltage) (Fig. 2). The depletion-zone generating surface can support charge separation, either by creating a selectively permeable membrane (as is the case with our gels) or by providing ionisable functional groups able to release mobile ions to the solution (as shown in our previous study).¹¹ Regarding permselectivity, an important feature supporting this mechanism of operation is surface porosity. In our experiments we used "aged" gels that were stored for a given period of time after gelation, because ageing consistently induced formation of larger depletion zones. Changes that occur on ageing result in gels having larger pores with clear lumen due to Ostwald ripening and partitioning of loosely associated polymer strands to the gel network.^{39,40} The same changes can be induced also by gentle drying. We adopted this approach in order to verify the effect of porosity on the gel's ability to generate a depletion zone. Our results show that the gel's internal negativity increases on drying (Fig. 2) as can be expected due to more functional groups exposed in larger pores free of shielding

Fig. 3 Representative images showing exclusion of microparticles (to the right) from the surface of a gel: a) ALG (exclusion distance, $d = 80 \mu\text{m}$); b) AG, $d = 83 \mu\text{m}$ and c) FU, $d = 119 \mu\text{m}$.

Fig. 4 Changes in voltage with distance from the gel's surface (0 μm) on an electrode moving from the bulk solution (zero mV reading), throughout the depletion zone (voltage drop and stable negative reading) to the gel's body (sudden increase in negativity). Color-coded traces show examples of superimposed voltage readings for ALG (blue); AG (orange) and FU (green) gels. Depletion zone widths determined either by microparticle exclusion or voltage drop correspond to each other.

unbounded polymer strands. Together with gel's negativity increases also depletion zone voltage and width (Fig. 5). Changes in voltage range from $(-10.6 \pm 0.7) \text{ mV}$ to $(-12.5 \pm 1.0) \text{ mV}$ for AG HE; $(-8.7 \pm 0.1) \text{ mV}$ to $(-12.8 \pm 0.8) \text{ mV}$ for 2.5 % ALG and $(-19.8 \pm 0.4) \text{ mV}$ to $(-23.5 \pm 1.6) \text{ mV}$ for a FU gel with 2.5 % fucoidan content. Corresponding increase in the depletion zone's width for respective gels reaches $(7.0 \pm 2.3) \mu\text{m}$ for AG; $(8.7 \pm 2.1) \mu\text{m}$ for ALG and $(9.2 \pm 2.3) \mu\text{m}$ for FU.

In our experiments, performed in water without added salt, ions subject to separation across the gel's interface come from dissolution of atmospheric CO₂, which provides hydronium and bicarbonate ions. H⁺ and HCO₃⁻ have very different diffusion coefficients, which enables them to effectively separate in space in aqueous solution when subject to a force driving their directional movement (chemical gradient, advection by osmotic pressure or electric force).⁴¹⁻⁴⁴ Different diffusion rates are essential for the ions to generate a liquid junction potential. Otherwise, ions could diffuse together through a charged barrier (here a gel pore) as an essentially electroneutral pair.⁴⁵ Potential (voltage) generation is a necessary requirement for ion and particle exclusion.^{46,47} In our experiments, effective separation of charges is confirmed by voltage vs. distance trace (Fig. 4). Voltage of the depletion zone (measured with respect to bulk) drops at the zone/bulk interface and stays constant

Fig. 5 Changes of the depletion zone voltage with depletion zone width for: gels immersed in DI water - solid lines (filled symbols) and partially dried (aged) gels in DI water - dashed lines (open symbols). Blue, round marks – ALG; orange, triangles – AG; green, square marks – FU. Correlations are logarithmic for all experimental conditions. Points along individual trend lines correspond to different preparations of a given gel type with the concentration of functional groups increasing on moving from bottom left to upper right.

within the zone width. This is expected for the electrically and/or chemically homogeneous space and confirms that the depletion zone does not have a diffusive character. Charges separated across this water layer in essence create a capacitor (Fig. 1). It has to be stressed however that oftentimes, the voltage within the zone would show an exponential increase in negativity on going from the bulk to a gel surface. Such potential gradient is expected for non-uniform ion distribution in a diffusive layer next to a charged interface or Donnan (selectively permeable) membrane.^{46,48} Yet in depletion zones the potential persists over a distance exceeding by orders of magnitude the one predicted by electrical double layer theory.⁴⁶ Discussion on specific parameters defining gradually changing vs. constant potential value within the zone is out of the scope of this manuscript. It can be suggested that constant voltage represents a specific time-window, where net exchange of ions between gel and solution is virtually non-existent due to a developed balance of forces (as illustrated in Fig. 1). All correlations described in this manuscript are based on constant voltage cases (as it avoids arbitrary choosing potential value representative for the zone). However, qualitatively all trends are the same for both diffusive and electrically homogeneous zones.

Depletion zone voltage and concentration cell

The origin of electric potential difference persisting over a distance of micrometers between two parts of the same solution (the depletion zone and the bulk) without any physical barrier separating the two is still matter of debate.³⁰ In our experiments, depletion zone always shows negative voltage with respect to bulk solution. The zone voltage increases (becomes more negative) logarithmically with increasing zone width (Fig. 5 and 6). Width depends on separated ionic charges

Fig. 6 Dependence of the depletion zone's voltage on its width for gels without (solid lines, unshaded) and after exposure to CO₂ (dashed lines, shaded) supplied either internally (int.) – open symbols or externally (ext.) – filled symbols. Blue, circles – ALG; orange, triangles – AG; green, squares – FU. Concentration of functional groups increases along trend lines from left bottom to right upper corner. All correlations are logarithmic. Vertical (constant zone's width) line across points pertaining to a gel of given composition under internal or external CO₂ exposure highlights voltage change at the constant zone's width depending on the direction of the CO₂ gradient.

(ions in green, Fig. 1) subject to repulsion by the gel's surface. Yet, the voltage difference across the zone/bulk interface is argued here to depend on the imbalance of ionic solute concentrations between virtually electroneutral parts of the solution as previously suggested by Schurr.³⁰

Between ion-depleted and bulk solution, for which we can measure voltage gradient, there is a sustained concentration gradient. The two neighbouring solutions do not mix due to a balance of forces that prevent ions from entering the depletion zone.^{12,14,16} Yet, the system strives toward chemical equilibrium (concentration equilibration) and effectively acts as a concentration cell.⁴⁹⁻⁵¹ In a concentration cell, there is a logarithmic dependence of the voltage on the concentration gradient, as described by Nernst equation [eq.1]:

$$\Delta V = \frac{RT}{nF} \ln \frac{C_{low}}{C_{high}},$$

(where: V – voltage, R – gas constant, F – Faraday's constant, T – temperature (K), n – number of moles of electrons transferred in the reaction, C_{low} and C_{high} – concentration of less and more concentrated solution, respectively).

In our experiments, exact concentrations of ions are unknown, but concentration gradient determines the degree of charge separation (by providing chemical driving force for ion flow) that further translates into zone width (Fig. 1, unbalanced (in green) anions in solution being repelled by the gel surface). Therefore, logarithmic dependence can be found between depletion zone size and voltage of a concentration cell created by ion-depleted and bulk solution (Fig. 5 and 6). Voltage is expected to be a logarithmic function of concentration gradient whether we consider electrochemical concentration cell,

Table 1. Electric potential difference (mV) between the external reference solution (R), depletion zone (Z) and bulk solution (B) for different combinations of reference and experimental solutions.

solution		Voltage (mV)		
Reference (R)	Bulk (B)	Depletion zone - V_z	Bulk - V_b	$V_b - V_z$
DI water	DI water	66.1 (± 30.2) [*]	81.8 (± 29.6) [*]	15.7 (± 0.7)
DI water	0.1 mM KCl	34.4 (± 2.3)	61.9 (± 2.3)	27.5 (± 0.6)
DI water +CO ₂	DI water +CO ₂	-18.8 (± 0.5)	9.3 (± 0.4)	28.0 (± 0.2)
0.1 mM KCl	0.1 mM KCl	-20.5 (± 0.3)	6.4 (± 0.6)	26.9 (± 0.3)

^{*}large experimental errors between individual measurements result from the fact that DI water is both poorly conductive and continuously changing due to interaction with atmospheric gases

Donnan (permselective) membrane or membrane potential of a living cell.⁴⁵ Description of the depletion zone system with the use of respective equations (as derived also by Schurr)³⁰ is justified as we deal with a long-lived state during which parameters of the system stay constant. Time evolution of depletion zones has been described in other works.^{11,46} Only for FU width vs. voltage correlation is almost equally well fitted by logarithmic and by linear trendline. As we will discuss later, FU is a source of protons that do not determine zone size (lack of mobile counterions that could be repelled by the surface), but contribute to concentration gradient and by leaving behind their fixed counterions to increased surface charge.

The energy can be harvested from the concentration cell if a connection allowing for electron flow is provided (in our case via electrodes and electrometer). In the concentration cell,⁴⁹⁻⁵¹ in the less concentrated solution generation of ions occurs due to electrode oxidation, while in the more concentrated solution ions are removed via electrode reduction. Therefore, electrons flow from the less concentrated solution (negative terminal) to the more concentrated one (positive terminal). The concentration gradient is the underlying reason for the voltage of the depletion zone being negative with respect to the bulk. A similar scenario has been previously suggested by Schurr.³⁰ To prove the concept we have performed a series of experiments in which voltage of the depletion zone and bulk solution was measured against an external reference solution (Table 1). We could show that when the reference solution has lower concentration of ions than our experimental system (containing depletion zone-generating gel), both the depletion zone and bulk solution show positive voltages. This is the case for DI water used as a reference and a gel immersed in 0.1 M KCl and for both containers filled with DI water. In the latter configuration, some impurities coming out from the gel

effectively create a solution of higher concentration with respect to the external DI water reservoir. In the case of equimolar solution concentration in the interconnected dishes (either CO₂ saturated water or 0.1 mM KCl; shaded rows in the table), the depletion zone reads negative while bulk solution positive, as expected for the region depleted and enriched in ions with respect to the reference. Yet, the potential difference between the depletion zone and neighbouring bulk solution ($V_b - V_z$) does not depend on the point of reference and corresponds to the values measured in the system with internal reference (used as a standard configuration throughout this work). It should be noted at this point that the effective voltage of the depletion zone will always be negative with respect to its adjacent (more concentrated) parent solution.

It is not clear at the moment if the oxidation/reduction occurs at the electrodes, as in a standard concentration cell scenario, or in fact results from spontaneous dissociation⁵² followed by the oxidation of water. The former should be unlikely due to the concentrated KCl serving as a salt bridge. Yet water oxidation can occur under the influence of an electric field and pH gradient, and was shown to happen spontaneously at the interface of pure water microdroplets.⁵³ The electric field and proton gradient are both generated in our system due to the separation of charges across depletion zone and the accumulation of protons at the zone/bulk boundary (addressed in the following sections). The possibility of autodissociation and redox reactions of water in the depletion zone should be further explored and will be the focus of our forthcoming studies. We already have preliminary data supporting this hypothesis.

Ion concentration gradient – a driving and limiting factor

Depletion zone formation requires ionic species and a force driving their movement across the permselective interface.^{7,46} To further verify this principle in our biomimetic system we performed experiments with CO₂ gradient imposed over $-\text{OSO}_3^-$ and $-\text{COO}^-$ containing gels. Our results show that increased concentration and gradient of CO₂, generated either by internal (to gel's pore water) or external (to bulk solution) supply of CO₂, promotes the formation of a larger depletion zone of higher voltage (Fig. 6). Under the influence of CO₂ depletion zone can reach up to $(131.0 \pm 2.4) \mu\text{m}$ and $(-33.6 \pm 1.6) \text{mV}$ for FU; $(99.6 \pm 2.0) \mu\text{m}$ and $(-18.6 \pm 0.8) \text{mV}$ for AG; $(87.6 \pm 2.7) \mu\text{m}$ and $(-17.5 \pm 0.6) \text{mV}$ for ALG. The logarithmic relationship between zone width and voltage and linear dependence of zone size on the gel's internal negativity were preserved in the presence of additional CO₂ (Fig. 2 and 6). Yet, in spite of the fact that the gel's negativity diminishes under the influence of CO₂ (some of the gel's functional groups are screened by protons coming from CO₂ dissolution), the depletion zone expands (Fig. 2). This observation supports the idea that ionic species providing charges that can separate across the interface (here H⁺ and HCO₃⁻) are a limiting factor mainly responsible for the depletion zone formation¹⁶. In other words, a charged interface can repel ions (and lead to zone formation) only if those are present. This

Fig. 7 Dependence of the depletion zone width (μm) – solid lines, open symbols; and voltage (mV) – dashed lines, filled symbols; on conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) of the depletion zone-inducing gel: ALG – blue, circles; AG – orange; triangles; FU – green; squares. Width is best fitted by exponential and voltage by linear correlation with conductivity.

underlines the fact that depletion zone formation is not due to water-surface interaction, but is driven by ion separation across the interface for which a concentration gradient (a driving force) must exist. It is interesting to note that dynamic CO_2 gradients are commonly generated across biological interfaces of metabolizing cells or gas-exchanging tissues.

Charge gradients and concentration gradients – size and voltage

Our experimental results show that depletion zone voltage depends on the direction of CO_2 concentration gradient, while the width of the zone does not (Fig. 2 and 6). This confirms our considerations regarding the mechanism of ion depletion and voltage generation. Size is determined by electrostatic interaction limited by the concentration of mobile ions available for separation at the gel/water interface (here the same for internal and external CO_2 supply). Voltage, on the other hand, depends on the concentration gradient between the depletion zone and the bulk solution. Therefore, introducing extra CO_2 to the bulk results in a higher concentration gradient (and larger potential difference for the same zone size) with respect to CO_2 supply to the gel's porous water (not interfacing with the bulk) (Fig. 2 and 6). The specific dependencies of the depletion zone voltage and size on different factors are also reflected in their correlation to the gel's conductivity (Fig. 7). Conductivity of the gel supports ion transport within the gel's network and therefore adds to a driving force for charge separation. The key for effective charge separation is diffusion across the interface at different rates (Fig. 1).^{41-44,47} Studied gels with anionic functional groups easily conduct protons, thus further supporting their spatial separation from slowly diffusing bicarbonate anions. Our results show that for a given conductivity the width of the depletion zone is virtually the

Fig. 8 Dependence of the positive voltage registered at the depletion zone/bulk solution interface (region (a) in Fig. 1) on internal negative voltage of a gel, under internal (int.) – filled symbols, or external (ext.) – open symbols, CO_2 supply. ALG – blue, circles; AG – orange, triangles; FU – green, squares. Individual measurement points correspond to gels with varying concentration of functional groups (increasing with a gel's negativity).

same for one-component gels, ALG and AG. This observation further confirms that width of the zone depends on the non-balanced (separated) charges subject to repulsion by the surface. Therefore, if the concentration gradient (driving ion flow) is kept constant, the propensity of a surface to generate depletion zone can be judged from its ability to transfer (conduct) ions away from their counterions. The ions left in the solution can then be repelled by the surface of the same charge (Fig. 1, green-coloured anions repulsed by the negatively charged gel). At the same time, the voltage of the zone for a given conductivity is different for different gels. Voltage increase per unit conductivity is larger for $-\text{OSO}_3^-$ -containing gels than for alginate with its $-\text{COO}^-$ groups and follows the order $\text{ALG} < \text{AG} < \text{FU}$. Such a trend can result from different dissociation constants of sulfate and carboxylate groups with the former giving off their protons much easier than the latter.⁵⁴ Those H^+ separated from their fixed $-\text{OSO}_3^-$ counterparts can diffuse to the bulk solution and add to the ion concentration gradient defining voltage between the depletion zone and the bulk. Yet they do not contribute to increase of free negative charges in the solution (their counterions are immobile) that could be repelled from the surface and define zone width. Outward diffusion of protons from the gel's network, supported by the gel's conductivity⁵⁵, can also explain the steepest voltage change with zone size for FU gel followed by AG and ALG (Fig. 5).

Concentration of charge at depletion zone/solution interface

High dissociation constant of $-\text{OSO}_3^-$ translates into the effectiveness of sulfate-containing structures to generate depletion zones of larger voltage (with respect to the bulk), but also with higher capacitance (across the depletion zone). Extra protons coming from dissociation of functional groups and diffusing to the bulk become separated from their fixed

Fig. 9 Changes in the depletion zone's negativity (mV) – filled symbols; and positive voltage registered at the depletion zone/bulk solution interface (mV) – open symbols (shaded area), with solution's pH (adjusted with HCl). ALG (2.5 %) – blue, circles; AG (HE) – orange, triangles; FU (2.5 % fucoidan) – green, squares. A depletion zone's voltage dependence on pH is fitted by power function (dashed lines) in a region of pH from 4.1 to 5.9. Positive voltage (shaded area, dashed lines) shows logarithmic dependence on pH in the whole pH range covered in the experiments. As discussed in the text, those different trends result from the depletion zone's dependence on the presence of bicarbonates and positive voltage's on proton concentration.

counterions by the water layer largely free of ions, thus in essence creating a capacitor (Fig. 1). In fact, we can register cations gathering at the depletion zone boundary interfacing bulk solution. This is expressed in a narrow zone of positive voltage measured at the depletion zone/bulk solution interface (region (a) in Fig. 1) under increased concentration of ions in the system (introduced by CO_2 , KH_2PO_4 or occasionally observed next to FU gels) as shown on Fig. 8, 9 and 10. The magnitude of this positive voltage increases with increasing negativity of the gel for external CO_2 supply and decreases on increasing negativity of the gel for internal CO_2 supply (Fig. 8). These opposite trends can be understood by considering that positive voltage is generated by protons from CO_2 dissolution that gather at the boundary of the depletion zone (Fig. 1, region (a)) due to the attraction by the gel's negativity (Fig. 1, region (b)). The force of attraction is stronger for more negative gels, therefore, when CO_2 is added to the bulk, more protons pre-concentrate at the interface of the depletion zone surrounding more negative gel. When CO_2 is introduced to the gel's pore water, more protons are held within the gel's network and are restricted from diffusing out on increasing concentration of the gel's negatively charged functional groups. In other words, when the gel possesses higher concentration of fixed negative charges, it can hold more protons (that come from CO_2 dissolved in the gel's porous network and tend to diffuse outward) and/or it can attract more protons from the bulk (that will gather at the depletion zone/bulk boundary). In fact, pre-concentration of solutes and particles is a recognized feature of the depletion zone.^{12,16,56,57} Existence of positive voltage at the zone/bulk boundary is, to the best of our knowledge, reported here for the first time, although experiments with pH sensitive

Fig. 10 Changes in the depletion zone's negative voltage (mV) – non-shaded, bottom; and positive voltage at the depletion zone/bulk solution interface (mV) – shaded area at the top; with increasing concentration of KH_2PO_4 without (solid lines, filled symbols) and with fixed pH (dashed lines, open symbols). ALG – blue, circles; AG – orange, triangles; FU – green, squares.

dyes already indicated respective proton pre-concentration.⁵⁸ If a similar proton-enriched layer is generated next to $-\text{OSO}_3^-$ -rich glycocalyx coating of red blood cells (RBC) and vessels, it can support frictionless blood flow based on charge repulsion. Such considerations are in agreement with recent reports on extracellular voltage existing next to RBC.^{33,59} Further to this end, our previous results showed that water dipoles aligned between oppositely charged terminals of the depletion zone are more resistant to hydrostatic and osmotic pressure (effectively interfacial water does not flow).¹² This alignment therefore may create an additional physical barrier aiding RBC separation and flow.

Ion diffusion rates, charge separation and liquid junction potential

Experiments with CO_2 indicate that the presence of ions that can selectively partition to the interface determines formation of the depletion zone. In order for the separation of charges to occur over the extended distance (the depletion zone may have hundreds of micrometres) there are specific prerequisites: a force driving ion flow across the interface and the chemical identity of the ions enabling them effective spatial separation on directional movement in water. In our experiments, driving force is generated in the form of a chemical gradient, with different CO_2 concentrations inside and outside the gel. Regarding chemical identity of ions, the dissolving CO_2 was previously shown to be able to generate distinct positive and negative regions in aqueous systems.^{41,43,44,48} It was due to protons that diffuse in water at the fastest rate among ions and bicarbonates that cannot immediately follow their counterions. Different diffusion rates across a liquid junction (interface of solutions of different concentrations) results in ionic charge separation and generation of junction potential,⁶⁰ according to [eq 2]:

$$\Delta V = (t_+ - t_-) \frac{RT}{nF} \ln \frac{C_{\text{low}}}{C_{\text{high}}}$$
 where all symbols have the same meaning as in [eq. 1], while t_+ and t_- are transference numbers (describing ion fluxes) of the cation and anion respectively.

Please note that junction potential is not responsible for the measured depletion zone potential, as the former implies negative charge in the bulk (according to the direction of ion migration, Fig. 1). Nevertheless, junction potential *de facto* controls depletion zone formation by generating electric repulsive force between the liquid junction negative terminal (bulk, green coloured anions in Fig. 1) and the gel's negative surface.

To further support the notion about the importance of a driving force and different diffusion rates of ionic species in depletion zone formation, we performed experiments at different pH levels (adjusted by HCl) and different concentrations of KH_2PO_4 in bulk solution. Experiments with varying pH revealed that at a given pH value the depletion zone voltage is virtually the same, regardless of the fact if pH was determined by CO_2 or by HCl. Generally, with increasing proton concentration (lowering pH) the depletion zone expands and its voltage increases in magnitude (Fig. 9). Very notably however, this effect of pH evidently stagnates below $\text{pH} = 4$ and further decrease in pH does not induce zone enlargement anymore. At the same time, more protons are still gathering at the depletion zone/bulk interface as indicated by increasing the positive voltage measured at this boundary (Fig. 9). $\text{pH} = 4$ is exactly the point below which concentration of bicarbonate ions becomes virtually negligible in solution according to CO_2 speciation in water.⁶¹ Therefore, H^+ accompanied by Cl^- with diffusion rate of the latter being much higher than that of HCO_3^- are not efficient in creating depletion zone phenomena. In the case of KH_2PO_4 , at a fixed pH (constant proton concentration) increasing the concentration of KH_2PO_4 , giving rise to more H_2PO_4^- anions in the solution, promotes depletion zone expansion (as expressed in its increasing voltage, Fig. 10). Therefore, H_2PO_4^- with its diffusion rate much lower than that of H^+ is an effective counterpart in depletion zone formation. It is interesting to note that in relation to cellular environment, both HCO_3^- H_2PO_4^- are so called impermeant intracellular metabolites⁴⁵ and as such can give rise to junction potentials and consequently depletion zones across (next to) a charged membrane permeable to their counterions.

Driving force - depletion zone as a non-equilibrium process

The spatial extent of electrostatic interactions, as invoked in this work to explain depletion zone formation, diminishes with increasing ionic strength. Indeed, according to the expectations, it was commonly observed that a depletion zone's width shrinks with increasing background electrolyte concentration.⁴⁶ We performed experiments with KH_2PO_4 to show that the zone can in fact expand with increasing ionic strength, if the electrolyte is not homogeneously distributed in the system (gradient) and provides ions of different diffusion rates that can effectively separate in space on crossing the surface. Addition of low concentration of KH_2PO_4 completely prevents depletion zone formation in the system in which it was otherwise present (Fig. 10). To understand this result it is necessary to consider the driving force and the ionic nature of separated species. In

experiments performed in pure water, the only ions (apart from some arising from auto-dissociation of water) come from dissolving atmospheric CO_2 . Electrostatic repulsive force acts on bicarbonate anions approaching a negatively charged gel's surface following their proton-counterions. Electrostatic interactions are effectively screened with increasing ionic strength. This screening effect is described by Debye length defining distance over which charges may interact with each other.⁴⁹ The increasing ionic strength of the solution by means of KH_2PO_4 reduces Debye length and hampers the generation of the depletion zone by decreasing the possible distance of electrostatic repulsion. Very notably, further increase in ionic strength and KH_2PO_4 concentration brings about restoration and growth of the depletion zone (Fig. 10). This is because simultaneously with increasing ionic strength, the concentration gradient of KH_2PO_4 across the gel's interface – a driving force for ion directional movement (affecting ion transference as described by [eq. 2]) – also increases. This chemical force overwrites the screening effect. Correlation between KH_2PO_4 concentration and the zone's voltage is logarithmic as expected for a concentration cell according to [eq. 1]. These experiments clearly highlight that the depletion zone phenomenon does not behave in the same way as an electric double layer (EDL) which shrinks with increasing ionic concentration. It was suggested that extension of the zone greatly exceeding Debye length might be due to specific geometry of the system (mainly nanochannels).⁶² Our results showing depletion zone expansion with increasing ionic strength illustrate the importance of a driving force (here concentration gradient) in effective charge separation over extended distance. The prerequisite for driving force also indicates that depletion zone formation is a non-equilibrium process (as it relies on non-equilibrium junction potential). It can manifest itself in a prolonged stable transient state, yet it is not an intrinsic property of the surface and its interaction with water, but requires an input of energy to persist (e.g., in the form of chemical energy due to concentration gradient) and as shown in our previous work can vanish with time.¹¹

Conclusions and perspectives

Relationships unravelled in this work strongly support the adopted mechanism of depletion zone formation (as schematically depicted in Fig. 1): (i) cations and anions of different diffusion rates separate in the solution, generating junction potential, on flowing toward and then across the permselective gel's interface (a force driving the flow, e.g. chemical gradient, is a necessary requirement), (ii) ions of the same sign as that of gel's functional groups are repelled from the interface after their counterions penetrated the gel (charged gel network shields electrostatic attraction between separated mobile ions thus stabilizing junction potential), (iii) opposite charges become effectively separated across the depletion zone extending from the gel's surface. A capacitor configuration with terminals defined by fixed surface charges and by mobile ions enriched at the depletion zone boundary with the bulk is established. Adjacent solution's regions largely

devoid of and enriched in ions generate electric potential difference at the depletion zone/bulk interface with less concentrated solution becoming the negative terminal. To the best of our knowledge, the experimental evidence for this mechanism of voltage generation within the depletion zone is provided here for the first time. Furthermore, implications of liquid junction potential and importance of different diffusion rates of separating ions are explicitly considered in this work.

Our results show that it is possible to control depletion zone size and voltage according to the predictions based on the proposed mechanism of the zone formation. In our work we use biologically relevant triggers (CO_2 and KH_2PO_4) and gels with functional groups abundantly present in the glycocalyx ($-\text{OSO}_3^-$ and $-\text{COO}^-$) with the aim to relate the depletion zone to similar phenomena found in biological systems. Our results suggest in particular that a CO_2 (a respiratory gas) gradient existing across glycocalyx-coated vascular lining may support development of a recognised depletion region – the endothelial surface layer – effectively excluding blood cells and plasma solutes. Further to this end, efficacy of $-\text{OSO}_3^-$ in promoting voltage and charge separation across the zone, may relate to the unique importance of the high concentration of sulfate groups within the glycocalyx and to the anticoagulant properties of heparin. A sulfate-rich coating on red blood cells (RBC) may promote the development of a depletion zone, effectively preventing RBC from coagulation and supporting blood flow by the electrokinetic motion of RBC.

In biological systems, a concentration cell, formed by the depletion zone interfacing more concentrated solution, may potentially generate electron flow if redox centres are present in the two compartments. This may have profound implications for a system's bioenergetics. In fact, it has been suggested that effective charge separation across cell membranes based on electron transfer in redox reactions (murburn effect)⁶³ can contribute to resting and action potential development.

Author Contributions

MK has conceptualized and supervised the project, performed data analysis and written the original manuscript. SW performed laboratory analysis and contributed to data interpretation. SN supervised laboratory work, conceptualized methodological aspects, contributed to data interpretation and manuscript editing.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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